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How to master Kanji easily and effectively

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Introduction:

Kanji is just one component of the far more extensive and complicated Japanese language. Initially, studying kanji is like seasoning a dish. Certainly, even without the spice, food is still edible and gives the energy one needs to continue moving forward. Nevertheless, question arises is it delicious and would somebody serve it to other friends? Probably the answer will be in negative. Yet, the suggestion should not be given that one cannot survive in Japan without studying kanji. Nonetheless, learning kanji will unquestionably improve the comprehension of the Japanese language and make life in Japan simpler. Many starting Japanese learners make the usual criticism that kanji are too difficult. Nonetheless, this does not diminish the significance of knowing kanji. Kanji is ubiquitous in Japan. In fact, it appears on menus, signage, and even names. If one wants to live in Japan for a lengthy period of time, it is not sufficient to know how to speak Japanese or read hiragana. Also, if one chooses to work in Japan in the future, he must know kanji. In this paper, we'll discuss some excellent kanji study suggestions that can make kanji bit easier and effective to learn.

Analysis:

Learning kanji is not required to speak Japanese well. One might learn Japanese simply by watching Japanese plays. Yet, learning kanji is essential for various reasons. One does not really know the language until he can read and write it. This is taken for granted in languages using the same alphabet as English, such as Spanish and German. Yet learners of languages that do not, such

as Arabic and Korean, must also devote time to reading. This implies that Japanese language students will have their heads turned by the incredible world of kanji.

If one knows the kanji, he can guess the meanings of new words as you learn them. Kanji is comparable to the English suffixes. For instance, we know that a word beginning with "re-" indicates "again." A word beginning with "un-" signifies "not," whereas a word ending in "-able" signifies "can." Kanji characters are comparable to these suffixes. Each has its own meaning, and it is simpler to comprehend new words if you are familiar with their meanings.

If one ever wants to reside in Japan, he will need to learn kanji in order to navigate the country. One would be shocked at how few English signage there are, particularly outside of large cities. In addition, he'll need to be able to understand the entries on restaurant menus (they won't always have photos) and the product descriptions when one shops. Even if somebody is just visiting Japan, being able to understand basic signs and instructions in the language can give you a great deal of confidence. The process of learning kanji will take time, but as one acquires more knowledge, he will be able to use the sense of achievement to continue. One will finally be able to recognize all of the kanji that previously seemed so strange!

Kanji Learning Methods: Making Easy and Effective

Kanjis are Chinese characters that are part of the Japanese writing system, which also includes katakana and hiragana. They're the toughest element of learning how to read in Japanese since there are so many! To become literate in Japanese, one needs to know the about 2,000 "Standard Use Kanji" (常用漢字 / じょうようかんじ) which are found used in newspapers, magazines, books, ads and so on. That figure may seem frightening, but this paper shows the study tactics I used to get there below.

Japanese grammar as a whole. The number of hiragana and katakana is small in comparison to kanji, with only 46 of each. With consistent repetition, you can easily memorise them in under a week. There are a multitude of free and paid resources and apps available to assist you in learning them. Just get it done and let the feeling of accomplishment propel you into kanji with confidence.

02. Get to Know Kanji Radicals

Once you feel comfortable with hiragana and katakana, you can move on to kanji and radicals.

Kanji are composed of smaller components known as radicals. For instance, the kanji for “autumn” is 秋. Notice how it contains two clear parts:

- 禾 — This is the radical for “two-branch tree” or “grain.”
- 火 — This is the radical for “fire.” is the kanji for "autumn."

There are approximately 200 radicals, but learning only a few will provide you with clues to a surprising number of kanji. If one is familiar with these radicals, it is much easier to distinguish similar characters. Occasionally, one can also guess the pronunciation. Typically, characters with the same radical are pronounced differently. Checking out this comprehensive introduction to kanji radicals is needed to get started. To increase likelihood of remembering kanji containing radicals, one can examine groups of kanji that all contain the same radical. For instance, he could attempt to learn all the kanji that contain the water radical and also pertain to water. Begin with: 海 (うみ)

) — sea 洗う (あらう) — to wash

Once one have mastered these, he can move on to the kanji that use the water radical but don't have a direct connection to water, such as:

漢字 (かんじ) — kanji 漫

画 (まんが) — manga

Kanji	Reading	Radical and Meaning
読	よ / yo OR とう / tou OR どく / doku	To say: The radical is 言 and is located on the left. Therefore, the kanji is related to speaking.
悪	あく / aku OR わる / waru	Evil: The radical is 心 and it means heart or mind. This suggests it has to do with the heart, feeling or desire.

Examples of Radicals in Kanji

Similar to learning hiragana and katakana, it is best to get this out of the way early. Utilize the sense of accomplishment you gained by memorising this short list of radicals to propel one forward once more!

03. Rote Memorization

First of all, repeating something is the best way to learn a language. Students learn by doing things over and over again, like using flash cards or reading notes and chapters of books over and over again. This makes one want to read and write kanji over and over again. This is also a great way for people who are just starting out to learn kanji. He could also try practising stroke order with kanji that are easy to write. So, this will teach one the general patterns of stroke order and the most common radicals in kanji. One will also learn more about how kanji look and how their sounds change depending on whether they are connected to another kanji or not. The best part is that he won't have to worry when he sees the same kanji again!

04. Mnemonics of Kanji

Mnemonics are a learning technique that uses stories and associations to learn and store a new skill or memory. Mnemonics is a frequent method for learning kanji, and many kanji textbooks employ them to assist students memorise kanji. As a novice, I was taught kanji using this strategy, which aids in the memorization of certain kanji. Also, one can consider kanji as images of the words they represent. However, it can be difficult to decipher the meaning of each kanji simply by glancing at it, as these symbols were developed centuries ago. Yet, associating the meaning of a word with its image is one of the most effective ways to learn kanji. Here are some examples of how it might be accomplished :

Kanji	Reading	Meaning
田	た / ta OR だ / da	Field / Rice field: The square shape of the plot from rice fields very well with this kanji.
川	かわ / kawa	River: The three lines try to depict show the flow of a river.
山	やま / yama	Mountain: Mountains have their peaks and come in different elevations. The kanji depicts this difference in the height of mountains.
火	ひ / hi	Fire: Similar to the kanji 山 (yama), the kanji of fire draws its idea from the rise and fall of flames.
一 ; 二 ; 三	いち / ichi ; に / ni ; さん / san	One ; Two ; Three: These are some of the easiest kanji to remember. Think of them as 1, 2, and 3 fingers respectively.
Kanji	Reading	Meaning

more rapidly. One could even be able to determine the meaning of unfamiliar terms with its assistance. Japanese textbooks like the Genki textbook include jōyō kanji. Moreover, they are also readily available online in lists

06. Writing and Stroke Order

Writing is a crucial part of learning kanji. Several studies have shown that writing things down by hand helps we recall it. Writing practise is crucial when one considers all of this, as well as the fact that understanding stroke order might be crucial for understanding kanji. Several individuals have advised us to disregard stroke order while learning kanji, and I kind of agree with them. It is undoubtedly true that obsessing on details like stroke sequence will prevent you from remembering the character. I have, however, utilised stroke order to learn a few characters that, although having a similar appearance, simply wouldn't stay in my head. Despite the fact that we live in a digital age, writing will offer you the advantage you need to learn kanji more practically.

07. To maintain a Kanji Phrasebook

Here's a useful tip: anytime one encounters Japanese commercials, he can keep an eye out for them and note the kanji. Advertising is abundant in Japanese publications, catalogues, and variety shows, and it is often written in snappy, informal language. To use the fact that advertisements are made to stick in people's minds are his advantage! He can write down some of the kanji in his phrasebook after translating and memorising the slogan. He'll be reminded of the advertising whenever he encounters the kanji in another context, which will in turn jog him recall of the character's meaning.

08. To practice with Native Speakers

It's a good idea to make some Japanese friends and ask him/her to examine kanji writing if studying it. I've attempted penning some of the characters I have stored in my head, even though I've never officially studied writing, and every time it has caused others to chuckle and wrinkle their brows. Writing kanji involves numerous intricacies, and the best way to learn them is to have a native speaker correct your errors. It can be helpful to try emailing a pen pal to put your newly acquired kanji skills to use. Some websites like conversationexchange.com offers to locate some email conversation partners. One will get familiar with the most frequently used characters via ordinary discourse.

09. Learning of Most Used Kanji

In addition to the Jouyou kanji, one may get benefit by learning kanji he uses in everyday conversation but are not on the list. These are terms like printers, headphones, drapes, vases, lights, and career-specific words. Learning additional kanji of common terms may help him communicate with Japanese friends and family. This kanji can help him learn more kanji. Kanji may add excitement to correspondence with a Japanese pen buddy. One may just want to comprehend what his pen pal is saying without having to ask them to explain the kanji. But, starting Japanese by knowing the characters he'll use is sensible.

10. Learning Kanji of Vocabulary list

Each chapter of Genki's vocabulary lists contains kanji to learn. This includes stroke sequence, meanings, and pronunciations. Kanji that get this type of attention are typically significant and often utilised. Yet, textbooks like Genki also provide many vocabulary items without a chart demonstrating how the word is spelled in kanji and what other words utilise it. It's important to examine word list and kanji. It will improve one's vocabulary and kanji skills. As he masters language and finish chapter writing exercises, he'll probably use it more. Studying each word's

kanji on vocabulary list may be helpful to understand Japanese books, signs, newspapers, and other reading material better, and to master more kanji.

11. Using a Dictionary

It's useful to use a dictionary to learn any language. One needs to quickly search up unfamiliar words. One has to look for unfamiliar terms and comparable kanji. Hence, he will learn more kanji and understand them better. Without a computerized dictionary, searching is hard. If he knows the hiragana spelling, it's easy! One can find the romanized kanji and determine if the surrounding words use it. He should be able to find many words that employ the same kanji and understand its related kanji.

12. Using Kanji Learning Apps and Books

Apps teach autonomy, math, and coding, making them great study tools. There are many Kanji learning apps which offer learning kanji with strokes. These apps offer hundreds of kanji in Elementary 1 to Advanced categories. Japanese Kanji Study lets one deconstruct and explain radicals and use the term in sentences. If one doesn't like apps, he can try kanji books. These books contain hundreds of kanji with stroke order and memory techniques.

13. Trying Calligraphy

Calligraphy is known as 書道 (しょどう / shodou) in Japanese. If one is an artist or wish to learn kanji differently, calligraphy is a fantastic option. We've probably seen videos of someone carefully creating characters on thin white rice paper using an inkbrush. Graceful and beautiful. I've tried it several times and found it relaxing! Trying may reveal how messy it is. Putting something behind the rice paper prevents ink from bleeding onto the hard surface underneath (several layers of newspaper or construction paper would be ideal). If he spills ink, he may wish to wear an old shirt and jeans. Calligraphy pens are a cleaner alternative.

14. Japanese Literature

Reading is essential to language learning. No matter one's language or origin, he must read and write. So, practicing reading and writing is the only way to improve. Hence, reading Japanese frequently will help him learn more kanji and remember them better. I can't! "I don't know enough kanji." or "It's too hard. Translate everything." Both may be true. The idea is to push oneself to study more about kanji and how they are utilized in writing. Reading Japanese is challenging at first. If one keeps doing it, and he'll be great!

One may have read beginner-level content with easy-to-pronounce vocabulary. Learning kanji is comparable! Reading materials at this level can help to earn kanji. He can start reading children's books at N5. Yotsuba and Shirokuma Café are beginner-friendly manga with kanji reading. One can check them out. He can use rikaichan on Google Chrome for online reading. It's a great expansion for reading Japanese!

15. Studying Compound Kanji

As noted, studying kanji alone is boring. We look at a kanji and mutter its meaning and pronunciation to memorize it. One character without context is hard to recall. It's like trying to understand a dispute one walked into, even though the first thing his heard was, "It wasn't my fault!" I barely touched the elephant!" The dispute is over who scared the elephants at a nature park. Because kanji represent parts of words, learning them is similar to learning English. They usually appear with hiragana or another kanji. Here is an example of the kanji in the image below:

Kanji	Reading	Meaning	Word Combination

週	しゅう / shuu	Week	週末 ; Weekend
末	まつ / matsu	The end	
本	ほん / hon	Book	本屋 ; Book Store
屋	や / ya	Store	

Examples of Compound Kanji

16. Setting Realistic Goals

Even though studying kanji should be a habit, there is need to make reasonable goals. How fast? Is it realistic? If someone says he wants to learn all 2200-ish kanji to be "newspaper fluent" in a year. That involves learning six to seven new kanji daily. Can he learn seven new kanji daily, with meaning and readings, with his schedule? Yes, please! If not, he must set a more reasonable deadline. He may try two years. If one establishes an unrealistic goal early on and fail, he may stop. One should avoid that trap by starting too small or too big. Learning should be part of life, but not so much that he despises it.

17. Tracking Own Progress

Discovering own academic progress is inspiring. To determine Kanji learning level, it's needed to test oneself at the start and frequently as he learns.

Online tests include:

- JLPT Level Check—Kanji portion.
- MLC Kanji Level Check—This brief test estimates your kanji knowledge.
- Japanese Level Up—This site has several postings about proficiency testing.

Kanji (and Japanese) are fantastic since he can track your development. Learning reveals the language. Reading Japanese text gets simpler every time. Motivating! Tracking level of literacy is a less formal but highly satisfying way to progress.

Conclusion:

The key to learning kanji is developing a regular study habit. Consistency matters, even if he can only spare 15 minutes every day. It's necessary to keep up it and pay attention when one starts to notice results because his accomplishments will inspire him to achieve further success. Making it known to others is a great strategy to keep oneself on track. One may start a blog to document your progress toward Japanese literacy or post updates about his success on social media. He'll be too ashamed to fall short of his educational objectives. To encourage oneself to study kanji, a competition may be organized with other Japanese language students. One may decide on a time in a few months and then put each other to the test to determine who has improved the most. Another approach would be to assign each person a fixed amount of kanji to study, then hold a competition to see who can read or write them all down without checking first. Testing each other each week leading up to the deadline would help to stay current.